

B. Tech Seminar Report

Blockchain with Internet of things

**Submitted in partial fulfilment for the Degree of
Bachelor of Technology in
Computer Science and Engineering**

Submitted by

IMRAN RAZA

Reg No: MCE19CS045

Under the guidance of
Ms. HEMA S MAHESH

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Marian Engineering College

Thiruvananthapuram

DECEMBER 2022

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DECLARATION

I undersigned hereby declare that the project report “**Blockchain with Internet of Things,**” submitted for partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of degree of Bachelor of Technology of the APJ Abdul Kalam Technological University, Kerala is a bonafide work done by me under the supervision of **Ms. Hema S Mahesh**. This submission represents my ideas in my own words and where ideas or words of others have been included, I have adequately and accurately cited and referenced the original sources. I also declare that I have adhered to ethics of academic honesty and integrity and have not misrepresented or fabricated any data or idea or fact or source in my submission. I understand that any violation of the above will be a cause for disciplinary action by the institute and/or the University and can also evoke penal action from the sources which have thus not been properly cited or from whom proper permission has not been obtained. This report has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma or similar title of any other University.

Place

Signature

Date

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the report entitled “**Blockchain with Internet of Things**” submitted by **IMRAN RAZA (Reg No: MCE19CS045)** to the APJ Abdul Kalam Technological University in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the Degree of Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering is a bonafide record of the project carried out by him under our guidance and supervision. This report in any form has not been submitted to any other University or Institute for any purpose.

Place : Kazhakootam

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CONTENTS

<u>No.</u>	<u>TITLE</u>	<u>PAGE</u>
	ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	6
	ABSTRACT	6
	LIST OF FIGURES	7
1	INTRODUCTION	8
1.1	Introduction	8
1.2	Motivation	8
1.3	General Background	8
1.4	Objectives	9
1.5	Application	9
2	LITERATURE SURVEY	10
3	TECHNOLOGY STACK	11
3.1	Hardware Requirements	11
3.2	Software Requirements	11
3.3	Technologies Used	11
4	METHODOLOGY AND WORKING	14
4.1	Blockchain technology	14
4.2	Basic working	15
4.3	IOT architecture	15
4.4	Characteristic of Blockchain	16
4.5	Benefits of integrating blockchain with IOT	17
4.6	Challenges of blockchain with IOT	18
5	RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	19
6	CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK	20
6.1	Conclusion	20
6.2	Future Work	20

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ABSTRACT

The Internet of Things (IoT) has extended the internet connectivity to reach not just computers and humans, but most of our environment things. The IoT has the potential to connect billions of objects simultaneously which has the impact of improving information sharing needs that result in improving our life. Although the IoT benefits are unlimited, there are many challenges facing adopting the IoT in the real world due to its centralized server/client model. For instance, scalability and security issues that arise due to the excessive numbers of IoT objects in the network. The server/client model requires all devices to be connected and authenticated through the server, which creates a single point of failure. Therefore, moving the IoT system into the decentralized path may be the right decision. One of the popular decentralization systems is blockchain. The Blockchain is a powerful technology that decentralizes computation and management processes which can solve many of IoT issues, especially security. This paper provides an overview of the integration of the blockchain with the IoT with highlighting the integration benefits and challenges. The future research directions of blockchain with IoT are also discussed. We conclude that the combination of blockchain and IoT can provide a powerful approach which can significantly pave the way for new business models and distributed applications.

LIST OF FIGURES

No	TITLE	PAGE
4.1	Simple example of blockchain technology	14
4.3	IOT Architecture	15
4.4	Characteristics of Blockchain	16
4.5	Benefits of integrating blockchain with IOT	17
4.6	Challenges of Blockchain with IOT	18

CHAPTER - 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) has the ability to connect and communicate billions of things simultaneously. It provides various benefits to consumers that will change the way that users interact with the technology. Using a collection of cheap sensors and interconnected objects, information can be collected from our environment that will allow improving our way of living. Current IoT systems are built on centralized server/client model, which requires all devices to be connected and authenticated through the server. This model would not be able to provide the needs to outspread the IoT system in the future. Therefore, moving the IoT system into the decentralized path may be the right decision. One of the popular decentralization platforms is blockchain.

Integrating IoT with blockchain will have many benefits. The decentralization model of the blockchain will have the ability to handle processing of billions of transactions between IoT devices, which will significantly reduce the costs associated with installing and maintaining large centralized data centres and will distribute computation and storage needs across the billions of devices that form IoT networks. In addition, working with the blockchain technology will eliminate the single point of failure associated with the centralized IoT architecture. Moreover, integrating blockchain with IoT will allow the peer-to-peer messaging, file distribution and autonomous coordination between IoT devices with no need for the centralized server-client model.

1.2 MOTIVATION

Basically, the IoT is the connection and communication of different devices over the Internet. Billions of devices are connected together and we can control these devices over the internet. These devices or things can be control without being there and that will help people in life. These devices are composed of networking nodes whether serves or computer which are connected together to share their data. All devices are provided with sensors, which collect data that can be transmitted, stored, analysed, and presented in a useful way.

1.3 GENERAL BACKGROUND

The IoT concept is not new. In 1999, Ashton, who is the founder of MIT auto-identification centre has said “The Internet of Things has the potential to change the world, just as the Internet did. Maybe even more so”. Later in 2005, the ITU officially define the IoT as “a global infrastructure for the information society, enabling advanced services by interconnecting (physical and virtual) things based on, existing and evolving, interoperable information and communication technologies”.

A blockchain is a distributed database of records that contains all transactions that have been executed and shared among participating parties in the network. This distributed databased is called distributed ledger. Each transaction is stored in the distributed ledger and must be verified by consent of the majority of participants in the network. All transactions that have ever made are contained in the blockchain. Bitcoin, the decentralized peer-to-peer digital currency, is the most popular example that uses blockchain technology

1.4 OBJECTIVES

This paper provides an overview of integrating blockchain with the IoT system; this involves an examination of the benefits resulting from the integration process and the implementation challenges encountered. The ultimate goal of this work is to provide a detailed description of the benefits and the challenges that result from combing blockchain with IoT so as to make the decision whether to go with the decentralization for the IoT or not.

1.5 APPLICATION

For instance, the IBM Autonomous Decentralized Peer-to-Peer Telemetry project [7] leverages the blockchain to build a distributed network of devices. As for the ADEPT project, many other approaches are trying to design a solution that will be able to merge all the different blockchain based applications. Also, Slock.it introduced the first implementation of IoT and Blockchain using the Ethereum platform. It is so called Slocks to reflect real world physical objects that can be controlled by the Blockchain. They use the Ethereum Computer which is a piece of electronics that brings Blockchain technology to the entire home, making it possible to rent access to any compatible smart object and accept payments without intermediaries.

CHAPTER - 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. The IBM Autonomous Decentralized Peer-to-Peer Telemetry (ADEPT) project leverages the blockchain to build a distributed network of devices.
2. As for the ADEPT project, many other approaches are trying to design a solution that will be able to merge all the different blockchain based applications
3. Slock.it introduced the first implementation of IoT and Blockchain using the Ethereum platform. It is so called Slocks to reflect real-world physical objects that can be controlled by the Blockchain.
4. Blockchain in healthcare IoT application has introduced as a solution for many challenges facing healthcare sector.

CHAPTER - 3

TECHNOLOGY STACK

3.1. HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

- Processor: Intel i3-7th gen or more – Intel i3-7th gen is basically having 4 core and 4 thread which allow a decent performance.
- RAM: 4 GB or More – Most of the software's which is being used needs a minimum Ram of 4 GB or More.
- Hard disk: 5-10 GB free memory
- IOT devices

3.2. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

- IBM Watson IoT Platform
- Windows 7 or Higher

3.3. TECHNOLOGIES USED

3.3.1. Blockchain technology

Blockchain technology provides an efficient way of recording transactions or any digital interaction in a way that makes it secure, transparent, highly resistant to outages, auditable. This technology is still new and changing very fast; adopting it in the commercial market is still a few years off. However, decision-makers across industries and business functions should pay their attention now and start to investigate applications of this technology to avoid disruptive surprises or missed opportunities

There are many definitions for the blockchain. According to [5], the blockchain is defined as “a distributed database of records, or public ledger of all transactions or digital events that have been executed and shared among participating parties”. Each transaction in the public ledger is verified by consensus of a majority of the participants in the system. Once

entered, information can never be erased. The blockchain contains a certain and verifiable record of every single transaction ever made.

3.3.3. IOT_

The IoT is the connection and communication of different devices over the Internet. These devices are composed of networking nodes whether servers or computers which are connected together to share their data. All devices are provided with sensors, which collect data that can be transmitted, stored, analysed, and presented in a useful way. The current IoT architecture is built as a centralized model which is known as server/client model. In this model, all devices cannot talk to each other but talk to a centralized gateway instead. The centralized model has been used to connect a wide range of computing devices for many years and will continue to support small-scale IoT networks, however, it will not be capable of providing the needs to extend the IoT system in the future.

CHAPTER - 4

METHODOLOGY AND WORKING

4.1 PROPOSED SYSTEM

Blockchain technology

Figure 4.1: Simple example of Blockchain Technology

4.2 BASIC WORKING

Although the blockchain is still new and in experimenting stage, it is being perceived as a revolutionary solution that addresses modern technology issues such as decentralization, identity, trust, data ownership and data-driven decisions. The blockchain is generally a database that stores all the transactions in blocks. When a new transaction is created, the sender broadcasts it to the Peer-to-Peer communication channel to all other nodes in the network. The transaction is still new and not verified. When the nodes receive the transaction, they validate it and keep it in their ledger.

4.3 IOT ARCHITECTURE

Application layer encompasses IoT applications. There are many IoT application such as healthcare, smart cities, connected car, smart energy, smart agriculture and ...etc. Service support and application layer contains common capabilities which can be used by different IoT applications [14]. The Network layer includes devices such as routers, switches, gateways, and firewalls that are used to construct local and wide-area networks to provide Internet connectivity. In addition, it enables devices to communicate with one another and to communicate with application platforms such as computers, remote-control devices, and smartphones [13]. The device layer is similar to the physical layer of the Open System Interconnection (OSI) model of the network architecture. It is composed of physical devices and controllers that control objects. These objects represent things in the IoT that include a wide range of endpoint devices that send and receive a variety of information. For instance, sensors that collect information about the surrounding environment.

4.4 CHARACTERISTICS OF BLOCKCHAIN

4.5 BENEFITS OF INTEGRATING BLOCKCHAIN WITH IOT

4.6 CHALLENGES OF BLOCKCHAIN WITH IOT

CHAPTER – 5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In an IoT network, the blockchain can keep an immutable record of the history of smart devices. This feature enables the autonomous functioning of smart devices without the need for centralized authority. As a result, the blockchain will open a series of IoT scenarios that were difficult, or even impossible to implement without it. For example, by leveraging the blockchain, IoT solutions can enable secure, trust less messaging between devices in an IoT network [27]. In this model, the blockchain will treat message exchanges between devices similar to financial transactions in a bitcoin network. To enable message exchanges, devices will leverage smart contracts which then model the agreement between the two parties [20]. One of the most exciting capabilities of the blockchain is the ability to maintain a duly decentralized, trusted ledger of all transactions occurring in a network. This capability is essential to enable the many compliances and regulatory requirements of industrial IoT (IIoT) applications without the need to rely on a centralized model [6].

Many large organizations have started to adopt blockchain with IoT systems to get all benefits of the blockchain. For instance, IBM in partnership with Samsung has developed a platform ADEPT (Autonomous Decentralized Peer- To- Peer Telemetry) that uses elements of the bitcoin's underlying design to build a distributed network of devices, a decentralized IoT ADEPT uses three protocols-BitTorrent (file sharing), Ethereum (Smart Contracts) and TeleHash (Peer-To-Peer Messaging)-in the platform.

CHAPTER - 6

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 CONCLUSION

The IoT technology has extended that reached to every home in the universe. It has the ability to connect everyday objects to the Internet. Through cheap sensors, a lot of information can be collected from the surrounding environment that results in improving our life. However, current IoT architecture that based on server/client model has many issues that need to be addressed especially scalability and security. One of the solutions to address IoT issues is blockchain. Blockchain provides distributed peer-to-peer communication network where non-trusting nodes can interact with each other without a trusted intermediary, in a verifiable manner. In this paper, we provided an overview of integrating blockchain with IoT with highlighting benefits and challenges. The discussion also focused on future research directions. At the end, we can conclude that integrating blockchain with IoT can bring many advantages that improve many of IoT issues but at the same time, it introduces new challenges that should be addressed. There is still need more research to investigate implementing blockchain with IoT in more details.

5.1 FUTURE WORK

In future, blockchain will liberate and improve the productivity of society by digitizing the production relations. IOT and value anchoring technology can connect seamlessly the real world to the digital world.

The digital business contracts can be driven by machine automation to promote the resource allocation, value production and distribution in the real world and the digital society. Blockchain brings the changes from the “1.0 era” of e-cash and decentralized transactions to the “3.0 era” of valued Internet and decentralized social governance.

